

HUMAN HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT OF TRACE ELEMENTS BIOACCUMULATION IN BLACK MUSSELS (*MYTILUS GALLOPROVINCIALIS*)

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ABSTRACT

Black mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) represent a significant biomonitor aquatic species which can also pose a potentially harmful health risk impact to the consumers. The current study estimated the level of some trace elements including heavy metals and essential microelements in the muscle tissue of wild black mussel samples collected in 2020 and 2021 from the Southern and Northern Bulgarian Black sea coast. Data for bioaccumulation of the studied elements in the tested samples were compared to the maximum allowed concentrations stated by the Commission Regulation (EC) and Bulgarian legislation. An assessment of the human risk by calculation of the target hazard quotients (THQ) and hazard index (HI) was performed.

Key words: black mussel, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, trace elements, health risk.

Introduction

Black mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*, Lamarck, 1819) represents one of the major bivalve mollusks species in the Black sea. Quantitative estimates of mussel stocks along the Bulgarian coast were considered to be around 100 thousand tons (Petrova and Stoykov, 2011). Due to their nutritional value as a source of valuable proteins, vitamins, and minerals, as well as polyunsaturated fatty acids with health beneficial effects, their economic significance in the recent years was in progression (Pavlova *et al.*, 2020; Mititelu *et al.*, 2022). However due to their biology features and filter-feeding apparatus, the sea mussels have a capacity to bioaccumulate different xenobiotics and concentrate them to levels, that may significantly exceed the values in the environment (Szefer *et al.*, 2004; Stanković *et al.*, 2011; Pan and Wang, 2012). Based on this the assessment of trace elements including heavy metals in the mussels tissue could be used as an accurate bioindicator for environmental pollution, so called “mussel watch” (Goldberg, 1975; Rouane–Hacene *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore their widespread use into the human diet should be considered as a potential risk factor for intake of toxic and potentially harmful substances (Bat *et al.*, 2018). The potential health risk for the consumers can be estimated by calculation of the target hazard quotients (THQ) and hazard index (HI) (Peycheva *et al.*, 2021; Hossain *et al.*, 2022; Peycheva *et al.*, 2022a; Peycheva *et al.*, 2022b; Peycheva *et al.*, 2022c).

The aim of the current study was to determine the levels of Hg, Pb, Cd, As, Al, Zn and Mn in the edible part of wild *Mytilus galloprovincialis* from two locations from the western Black Sea area in terms of assessing the potential health risk for the consumers.

Materials and Methods

Samples collection

At each sample area 25 mussels of 48–58±4 mm each time were collected. In this study *Mytilus* mussels of similar size, weight and shape to ensure maximal uniformity in the applied methods were

used. The animals were rinsed with clean seawater and then placed in about 20 litres seawater for 24 hours to allow depuration. Following elimination of the gut contents the entire soft parts of the mussels were removed using stainless steel equipment. The soft parts were homogenised and deep frozen ($-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) until analysis.

The tested mussels were collected from wild catch in Varna and Burgas coastal area in 2020 and 2021.

Technical procedure

In a quartz crucible 10 g of the sample were placed previously measured on a Sartorius analytical balance with an accuracy of 0.0001 g and homogenized on a Vortex homogenizer. The samples were dried at $105\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ followed by microwave assisted acid digestion procedure (ETHOS UP High-performance Microwave digestion system, Milestone Inc). After digestion with HNO_3 an appropriate spectroscopy determination with Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS, Thermo Fisher TM) was performed. The method of analysis followed standard validated and internally developed validated methods for each chemical element. All measurements were performed in quadruplicate and the results were presented as mean values (X) (mg/kg w w) \pm standard deviation (SD).

Human health risk assessment

Target Hazard Quotient (THQ)

The THQ is used to determine the non-carcinogenic risk level due to pollutant exposure. To assess the health risk from metal contaminated black mussels, the THQ was calculated as per USEPA Region III Risk Based Concentration Table (USEPA, 2010) by using the following equation:

$$\text{THQ} = \frac{\text{Mc} \times \text{Ir} \times 10^{-3} \times \text{EF} \times \text{ED}}{\text{RfD} \times \text{BWa} \times \text{ATn}}$$

Mc – metal concentration in mussel tissue (mg/kg ww)]

Ir – average daily consumption (0.8 g/person/day) (FAO, 2023);

EF – exposure frequency or number of exposure events per year (365 days/year);

ED – exposure duration (30 years) for non-cancer risk as used by USEPA;

RfD – reference dose of individual metal ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$): (0.1 for MethylHg; 3.5 for Pb, 1 for Cd, 0.3 for As, 140 for Mn, 300 for Zn and 1000 for Al);

BWa – an average adult body weight (average 60 kg);

ATn – average exposure time for non-carcinogens.

THQ is an integrated risk index that compares the ingested amount of a contaminant with a standard reference dose. Non-significant risk effect is assumed for THQ value equals or less than 1. When the exposure level is greater than the RfD, the THQ is above 1, indicating that the exposed population is at health risk from the consumption of the studied species.

Hazard Index (HI)

The hazard index from THQs is expressed as the total of the hazard quotients (USEPA, 2010):

$$\text{HI} = \text{THQHg} + \text{THQPb} + \text{THQCd} + \text{THQAs} + \text{THQAl} + \text{THQZn} + \text{THQMn}$$

If the HI value is under 1 is assumed no human health risk.

Results and Discussion

Toxic metals and microelements levels in muscle tissue of Mytilus galloprovincialis

The obtained results for the concentrations of the tested toxic metals and microelements were summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Toxic metals and microelements concentrations (mg/kg wet weight) in muscle tissue of black mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) from Bulgarian Black Sea coast

Element	Varna region			Burgas region		Mean element concentration **	EC and Bulg. regulation permissible values
	August 2020	July 2021	November 2021	August 2020	July 2021		
Hg (X±SD)	< 0.05*	< 0.05*	< 0.05*	< 0.05*	< 0.05*	< 0.05	0.5
Pb (X±SD)	0.10 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.06	0.052 ± 0.005	0.10 ± 0.02	0.136	1.5
Cd (X±SD)	0.17 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.06	0.11 ± 0.02	0.206 ± 0.021	0.28 ± 0.06	0.211	1.0
As (X±SD)	0.90 ± 0.09	1.96 ± 0.39	1.43 ± 0.29	1.09 ± 0.11	2.08 ± 0.42	1.492	n/a
Al (X±SD)	18.76 ± 1.88	26.93 ± 5.39	478.89±95.78	42.75 ± 4.28	15.21± 3.04	116.508	n/a
Microelements							
Zn (X±SD)	10.05 ± 1.01	18.63 ± 3.72	32.35 ± 6.47	6.78 ± 0.68	13.11±0.21	16.184	n/a
Mn (X±SD)	1.18 ± 0.12	1.42 ± 0.28	24.48 ± 4.90	2.11 ± 0.21	1.09 ± 0.21	6.056	n/a

*Method detection limits; ** Mean value for all analysed samples used for estimation of THQ and H

The EC and national regulations postulated maximum permissible levels for Hg, Pb and Cd (Ordinance No 31, 2004; EC, 2006). In all of the tested mussel samples these metals were far below (fig.1 and 2). The mercury levels were below 0.05 mg/kg which is the method detection limit. The autumn Pb concentration exceeded almost 3 times the summer values which is demonstration of the seasonal variability. The same pattern was not presented for the cadmium. There were no significant differences between the investigated areas regarding Hg, Pb and Cd. On the other hand As concentrations showed some temporal variations. Severe spatiotemporal distinctions were detected in the levels of Zn, Mn and Al. Their reference ranges were between 6.78–32.35 mg/kg, 1.09–24.48 mg/kg and 15.21–478.89 mg/kg respectively. Despite the lack of certainty for the reasons for these substantial variations, an influence of environmental pollution degree can be hypothesized.

Figure 1: Lead (Pb) concentrations in the tested mussel samples compared to the EC reference value (mg/kg)

Figure 2: Cadmium (Cd) concentrations in the tested mussel samples compared to the EC reference value (mg/kg)

Variations in trace metals accumulation in bivalves according to the season and body size were suggested (Casas *et al.*, 2004; Mubiana *et al.*, 2005). Casas *et al.* (2004) reported that smaller mussels were with higher levels of trace metals than larger ones, while Saavedra *et al.* (2004) showed no major size-related differences in metal concentrations in the edible tissue of cultivated mussels *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. On the contrary, the seasonal variations in metal levels in bivalve species were demonstrated (Rainbow, 1999; Karayakar *et al.*, 2007). Higher concentrations in autumn and winter and relative decrease in summer were detected and can be attributed to physiological features or the reproductive cycle. Catsiki and Florou (2006) also reported seasonal variations concerning mainly Cu, Zn, Mn and Cr which are essential for the mussel physiology. Bat *et al.* (1999) clearly demonstrated the monthly variations in zinc, copper, lead and cadmium concentrations in samples from the Sinop coast of the Black sea. Results from different areas (Morocco) were in concordance (Azizi *et al.*, 2021). In the current study, seasonal fluctuations in metal bioconcentration were demonstrated with regard to Pb, Al, Zn and Mn. All of the above mentioned showed higher levels in autumn compared to the summer period.

Even more abiotic factors can affect the bioconcentration level of trace elements – effect of location within the intertidal zone, the pH of water, co-occurrence of metals, pre-exposure to metals, effects of the temperature and salinity (Azizi *et al.*, 2018). All these result in serious variations and potentially uncertainty in the final conclusions concerning the impact to human health risk.

The significant spatiotemporal variations in bioaccumulation of trace elements in black mussel and the different sea water pollution levels due to local specificity make the comparison of the results in various researches relative and of limited value. Available results (in mg/kg w.w) from the Bulgarian Black coast showed that the Cd levels were in the range of 0.044–0.090, Pb – 0.11–0.18, Hg – 0.08–0.32, As – 1.74–2.07 and for Mn – 1.24–2.70 (Stancheva *et al.*, 2012). More current results regarding the levels of legislation-regulated heavy metals in farm *Mytilus* mussels from the northern part of the Bulgarian shore indicated increased levels of Cd (0.355 ± 0.05 mg/kg) and decreased levels of Pb (0.046 ± 0.02 mg/kg) (Peycheva *et al.*, 2022a).

While the Hg levels in the current study were below, the concentrations of As were in the same range (As – 0.9–2.08). The levels of Pb and Cd represented a wider range (0.052–0.32 for Pb and 0.11–0.29 for Cd). A pronounced discrepancy with Peycheva *et al.* (2012) was demonstrated in the concentration of manganese with a range of 1.09–24.48 mg/kg. However, the element with the most substantial range variation and at the same time with the highest value was Al (15.21–478.89 mg/kg).

Food can be one of the main uptake sources for humans. Neurotoxic impact of aluminium were established and positive association between Al levels in drinking water and risk of dementia and Alzheimer's disease was postulated (Krewski *et al.*, 2007).

Jović *et al.* (2012) reported no statistically significant differences in the element concentrations between wild and cultivated mussels. The cited study also concluded that the estimated heavy metals concentrations were below the levels which can pose health risk for mussel consumers based on weekly consumption of 125 g ww mussels. However they found that Cd concentrations were the limiting factor for mussels as a food. The weekly consumptions of 0.64–1.2 kg of fresh wild and 0.84–1.2 kg of fresh cultivated mussel would be sufficient to reach the PTWI Cd, which may result in a risky weekly intake of Cd for longterm exposure. However study with similar design for the Bulgarian Black sea coast demonstrated higher levels for almost all of the tested metals in farm *Mytilus* compared to wild catch, as follow (mg/kg): Zn – 17.55–21.45 for wild and 19.02–29.87 for farm; Mn – 1.56–2.73 for wild and 3.22–3.24 for farm; As – 0.62–0.73 and 1.57–2.24; Cd – 0.14–0.16 and 0.32–0.64; Pb – 0.09–0.19 and 0.03–0.16 for wild and farm samples respectively (Peycheva *et al.*, 2021). The obtained in the current survey level of Pb, Cd, As for wild *Mytilus* samples were in wider range and with higher maximal values. The same was true also for the essential but potentially harmful elements like Zn and especially for Mn (highest value of 2.73 mg/kg vs. 24.48 mg/kg).

Complex scientific project for assessment of hazardous substances in Black sea biota in 2019 established high level of pollution toxic metals, in particular arsenic, cadmium and mercury more severe in *Rapana venosa* and mussel sampled in areas under the influence of Danube river and other rivers (Oros *et al.*, 2021). The amount of some trace elements (like Pb in *Mytilus galloprovincialis* collected from Sakarya River mouth, Turkey) were found above the permissible limits for human consumption. Levels of Cd and Pb in mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), sampled from different locations along Romanian coast, were below the Maximum Admissible Levels from European legislation (EC No. 1881/2006) with just one exception. In contrary the results obtained in another study form Istanbul area showed levels of As, Pb, Cd, Ni, and Zn in gills and digestive gland of *M. galloprovincialis* above the maximum limits (mgkg⁻¹), which were 0.67 for Cd, 6.9 for As, 0.79 for Pb, 2 for Ni and 42.6 for Zn (Türkoğlu *et al.*, 2022). These findings demonstrated the significance of sample locations and the potential heterogeneity in metal accumulation in different mollusks organs.

Health Risk Assessment

Target hazard quotients for Pb, Cd, As, Al, Zn and Mn and hazard index, estimated through the consumption of black mussel from the Black Sea are presented in Table 2. Since the mercury concentration is under the limit of detection, the THQ calculation was not performed.

Table 2: Risk values (THQ and HI) of each metal contaminant in muscle of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* from Black Sea (Bulgaria).

Risk value	Hg	Pb	Cd	As	Al	Zn	Mn
Target Hazard Quotient (THQ)	–	0.0001	0.001	0.0242	0.0006	0.0003	0.0002
Hazard Index (HI)	0.0264						

In this study the THQ and HI for consumers were less than 1 for all elements. Therefore, there is no health risk through the consumption of the tested black mussel.

Conclusion

Some heavy metals and essential element concentrations were determined in *M. galloprovincialis* samples from the Bulgarian part of the Black Sea. The data presented show that these levels were within the maximum acceptable limits set by European Union and Bulgarian health organizations. No toxic and essential elements were found to be considered as potential health hazards for consumers based on the THQ and HI. According to these results, the consumption of black mussel meat is safe for human health.

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